

MATCHING MATRIX AND FILLER DIELECTRIC CONSTANTS TO INCREASE DIELECTRIC BREAKDOWN STRENGTH

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1 Abstract

We investigate lightweight polymer matrix composite [PMC] capacitive devices capable of replacing bulky high energy pulsed power capacitors on mobile platforms. The glass fiber/polymer structural dielectric used in these capacitors often suffers from limited energy density due to premature dielectric breakdown, possibly precipitated by the mismatch in dielectric constant [ϵ'] at the glass/polymer interface. This mismatch effectively serves as an electrical stress raiser and may act as the critical flaw in dielectric breakdown. In this work we attempt to address this problem by modifying the dielectric properties of the matrix so as to more closely match the dielectric constant of the glass filler. Since it has been shown that, unlike larger reinforcements, nanometer scale reinforcements do not precipitate dielectric breakdown, we fill the matrix with high dielectric constant nanofiller in order to match the dielectric constant of the matrix with that of the micron-sized reinforcements. By reducing the mismatch in dielectric constant at the matrix-filler interface, we mitigate the buildup of field concentrations responsible for the premature breakdown events. The following study presents the improved characteristics in dielectric breakdown strength observed for PMCs composed of bisphenol E cyanate ester [BECy] monomer resin modified with nanometer sized barium titanate [BaTiO₃] particles, designed to produce a low viscosity slurry with a matching dielectric constant value to E-glass microsphere filler, $\epsilon' = 5.8$. Glass spheres are used instead of fibers to facilitate sample preparation.

2 Introduction

2.1 Structural Capacitors

Due to their excellent specific properties, composite materials have proven very successful in increasing the mass efficiency of structures under a variety of loading modes [1-8]. In this work we seek further increases in mass efficiency by designing materials that can perform multiple functions simultaneously. By eliminating or reducing the need for conventional materials that perform single, separate functions, this multifunctional materials approach offers system level mass/volume savings over conventional designs. For example, recent work has shown that structural capacitors can reduce overall system mass by combining weight intensive energy storage and structural functions, possibly enabling technologies such as electromagnetic armor and rail guns on mobile platforms[9, 10]

Structural capacitors are typically produced with a structural dielectric such as glass fiber reinforced polymers laminated with thin, conducting film electrodes. A critical performance metric for these devices is the energy density, which can be maximized either by raising the composite's dielectric constant and/or its dielectric breakdown voltage. Unfortunately, the presence of micron sized reinforcements in the composite dielectric often results in decreased dielectric breakdown strength [11]. The mismatch in dielectric constant at the interface between the reinforcement and the polymer acts as an electric field stress-riser, precipitating premature breakdown. However, research suggests that unlike micron-sized reinforcements, nanometer scale fillers do not reduce the breakdown strength [12, 13]. Therefore, nanometer fillers could be used to increase the

energy density in two ways. First, the increase in dielectric constant with increased filler content without the concomitant decrease in dielectric breakdown would result in an increase in energy density. Second, the nanometer scale filler could be used to tune the dielectric constant of the matrix to match that of the micron sized filler. Such a “nano-micro” composite would not suffer from the mismatch in dielectric constant and associated electric field concentration at the glass/polymer interface, resulting in increased breakdown strength.

In this work we study the effect of nanometer scale BaTiO₃ on the breakdown strength of BECy/glass composites. The BECy matrix is loaded with BaTiO₃ nanoparticles in order to raise the dielectric constant of the matrix to match that of the micron sized reinforcement. Composites with and without the BaTiO₃-filled matrix are manufactured across a range of glass contents and tested for their dielectric breakdown strength.

In the sections that follow, the design of the nano-micro composite is discussed first. An analytical model is used to determine the BaTiO₃ content necessary to raise the matrix dielectric constant to match that of the micron sized glass filler. Next, the procedure used to manufacture glass/BaTiO₃/cyanate ester composites is discussed. Finally the dielectric properties of these composites are tested in order to study the effect of nanofiller on the performance of structural capacitors.

2.2 Design of Nano-micro Composite for High Dielectric Breakdown Strength

In order to mitigate the dielectric breakdown of polymer matrix composites [PMCs], constituents must be chosen to minimize their difference in dielectric constant. Good match between matrix and filler dielectric constant values minimizes the phenomena of local field exclusion within the glass reinforcement and the associated local field enhancement in the polymer matrix[14]. For example, compared to neat polymers the dielectric breakdown strength of glass fiber reinforced PMCs is much lower[15]. This reduction is attributed to the dielectric constant mismatch at the matrix/glass interface which results in an electric field buildup

responsible for the catastrophic failure of the capacitor[16].

Instead of fibers, we use glass microspheres as model reinforcements in order to facilitate processing. For the matrix we use a cyanate ester. Most research and development in structural capacitor PMCs has focused on epoxy resins, while the application of cyanate ester resins as matrix material has not yet been thoroughly explored. Therefore, in this work we propose to increase the breakdown strength of conventional structural glass/polymer composites by matching the dielectric constants of the nanometer sized modified cyanate ester matrix and micron sized glass spheres.

Bruggeman’s symmetric mixture formula, Eq. (1), [17, 18] was used to estimate the content of BaTiO₃ nanoparticles necessary to match the dielectric constant of the BaTiO₃/BECy matrix to our desired filler, E-glass microspheres, which have a dielectric constant of $\epsilon' = 5.8$. From the model, the effective dielectric constant of the two phase system, ϵ' , is given by,

$$\varphi_1 \left(\frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon'}{\epsilon_1 + 2\epsilon'} \right) + \varphi_2 \left(\frac{\epsilon_2 - \epsilon'}{\epsilon_2 + 2\epsilon'} \right) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where φ is volume fraction, ϵ is dielectric constant, and subscripts 1 and 2 represent the PMC’s matrix and filler, respectively. From the equation above, we calculate the volume fraction of BaTiO₃ needed to produce a slurry with $\epsilon' = 5.8$. Taking the literature dielectric constant values of the glass, BECy, and BaTiO₃ to be 5.8, 4.0, and 150 respectively, the model predicts that dielectric constant of the BECy- nanocomposite matrix will match that of the glass fibers at a BaTiO₃ concentration of 10 vol. %, Fig. 1.

3 Processing and Dielectric Measurements

3.1 Materials

Commercially available BECy monomer resin, EX1510 with a specific gravity of 1.2, was purchased from TenCate Advanced Composites USA, Inc. (Morgan Hill, CA). Polymerization was initiated with the aid of the organometallic-based catalyst supplied by the manufacturer in a mass ratio of 3:100.

BaTiO₃ powder, with a nominal particle size of 50 nm and a specific gravity of 5.85, was obtained from Inframat Advanced Materials, LLC (Manchester, CT). The BaTiO₃ was kept in a vacuum oven at 76 °C prior to sample preparation, in order to remove any water molecules trapped on the powder surface. The presence of moisture during the cure cycle of BECy has been shown to negatively impact the dielectric and thermo-mechanical properties of the fully cured composite [19].

E-glass 6000E microspheres, with an average diameter of 6 μm, a dielectric constant of 5.8 at room temperature and a specific gravity of 2.54, were purchased from Potters Industries, Inc. (Valley Forge, PA). Since the glass spheres were highly agglomerated they were broken up using a mortar and pestle after which the powder was kept in a vacuum oven at 76°C prior to sample preparation.

3.2 PMC Wafer processing

In order to test the effect of BaTiO₃ nanoparticle content on composite breakdown strength, two sets of composite specimens were made with glass microsphere concentrations of 0 vol. %, 15 vol. %, and 30 vol. %. In the first set, the BECy matrix was used as received, without BaTiO₃ nanoparticles. In the second set, the BECy matrix was loaded with 10 vol. %, BaTiO₃ nanoparticles in order to achieve dielectric constant matching between the glass microspheres and the BECy/BaTiO₃ matrix.

The E-glass/BECy specimens were manufactured by homogenizing 14.55g of BECy and 0.45g catalyst with 5.6g and 13.6g of E-glass microspheres to make the 15 vol. % and 30 vol. % slurries, respectively. Homogenized slurries were prepared with the aid of a Thinky Centrifugal Mixer (model ARE 250, Thinky USA, Inc., Laguna Hills, CA), operating for periods of no less than 15 minutes with additional 5 minutes mixing times as needed for homogeneous dispersion.

The E-glass/BaTiO₃/BECy composites were manufactured from a slurry of BECy resin containing 10% by volume BaTiO₃ nanoparticles. The BaTiO₃/BECy slurry was prepared by homogenizing 8.20 g of BaTiO₃ nanometer sized

powder into 14.55 g of the low viscosity BECy monomer and 0.45 g of catalyst, as previously described for the BECy-glass specimens. Since BaTiO₃ is five times denser than BECy, high speed mixing is necessary to maximize the barium titanate's suspension time in the slurry. A moderate rise in viscosity was observed as ceramic and glass filler loading increases, however the resulting homogenized slurry still poured easily into the silicone rubber curing molds.

Preparation of the 15 vol. % and 30 vol. % E-glass-BaTiO₃/BECy PMC slurries required homogenizing 8.20 g of BaTiO₃ nano-powder with 6.28 g and 15.25 g, respectively, of E-glass microspheres prior to addition of the BECy monomer. In order to reduce the agglomeration of homogenous BaTiO₃ or E-glass powder pockets during planetary mixing, a LabRam ultrasonic mixer (Resodyn Corp., Butte, MT) was used at 65% intensity for 7 minutes to create a homogenous solid-solid mixture of the BaTiO₃ powder and E-glass microspheres. After addition of the 15.00 g BECy monomer-catalyst mixture, slurries containing the different loadings of E-glass (15 vol. % and 30 vol. %) were mixed, as described for the E-glass/BECy slurry, using the planetary mixer. As expected, the 15 vol. % and 30 vol. % E-glass slurries exhibited increased viscosity compared to the slurry without E-glass. However the viscosity increase did not prevent subsequent pouring and degassing. The homogenized slurries were poured into cylindrical silicone rubber molds and degassed in a vacuum chamber evacuated to -1 atm for 30 minutes to remove any air trapped during mixing. The nature of the silicone rubber molds prevented direct observation of any sedimentation that may have occurred during the degassing period. Nevertheless, in order to mitigate any sedimentation of the higher density fillers from the BECy resin during cure, the cylindrical molds were mounted onto a horizontal spindle, rotating at 80 revolutions per minute. The spindle was installed in a horizontally oriented overhead stirrer (model RW20, IKA Works, Inc., Wilmington, NC) and inserted into the oven through an unused exhaust port. The oven was ramped at 2° C/min. from room temperature to 90° C and samples were cured for 60 minutes. Post cure proceeded at the same ramp rate to 150°C and held for 2 hours to complete the cross-linking. The cured samples

were then allowed to gradually cool to room temperature before these were removed from the silicone rubber molds.

After cure, PMC wafers of diameter ca. 25 mm and thickness on the order of 200 μm were cut from the bulk sample using a low speed saw (Buehler, an ITW company, Lake Bluff, IL) equipped with a 500 μm thick diamond saw blade, set to 50% of maximum speed. Dielectric samples were subsequently sputter-coated with gold-palladium for 60 seconds (Desk V Sputter/Etch, Denton Vacuum LLC, Moorestown, NJ) to ensure good electrode contact. One face was sputtered using a 21mm circular mask while the other was completely covered, in an effort to mitigate edge effects, Fig. 2

3.3 Microscopy

Micrographs were collected using a reflected light microscope (MX 50 - 8 Inch, Olympus America Inc., Center Valley, PA) equipped with a 12 Megapixel digital camera (model 14.3 3-shot color, Spot Imaging Solutions, Diagnostic Instruments, Inc., Sterling Heights, MI) bundled with Spot Basic software V4.7. Optical images were collected at 1000x magnification.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) samples were prepared by sputter coating with a thin layer of gold (model Hummer XP, Anatech, Ltd., Alexandria, VA) for 35 seconds, then the sample region was framed with copper tape to reduce the amount of charging inherent to the specimen when the electron beam is on. SEM images were collected with a FE-SEM instrument (model S-4700, Hitachi High Technologies America, Inc., Dallas, TX) with FE PC-SEM software V3.6. Electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) SEM images were collected at x1000 for comparison to optical images.

3.3 Dielectric Constant

Dielectric constant and dissipative loss measurements were conducted at room temperature over the range of 1 Hz to 10^6 Hz using a broadband dielectric/impedance spectrometer (Novocontrol Technologies, Hundsagen, Germany) packaged with WinDETA V5.83 software. The dielectric spectrometer was fitted with a 20mm diameter bronze electrode that fit well within the perimeter

of the sputter coated electrode on the specimens. Four sample wafers from each bulk composite were measured in triplicate to determine a mean value of the dielectric constant; a total of 12 measurements per bulk PMC sample were collected.

3.5 Dielectric Breakdown Strength

Breakdown measurements were conducted using an insulating tower fitted with brass electrodes, Fig. 3, connected to a constant voltage ramp power supply, Glassman high voltage source (model FC60 power supply, Glassman High Voltage, Inc., High Bridge, NJ). The tower fit within the volume of a glass enclosed Faraday cage-style box designed to reduce the risk of electrical shock. The voltage was ramped at 500V/s until the specimen experienced catastrophic dielectric breakdown and could no longer support a potential. The PMC wafers were wetted with mineral oil to reduce the likelihood of dielectric breakdown through the air, circumventing the sample. The voltage data were collected at a rate of 120 Hz using LabView software and then analyzed with MS Excel.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Microscopy

Microscopy was used to characterize the dispersion of the various constituents. EBSD images revealed agglomerations of BaTiO_3 , seen as white circles in Fig. 5a, while grey circles and hollow circles represent the E-glass spheres embedded in and pulled out from the matrix. Using ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health), the PMCs' agglomerated BaTiO_3 content was estimated based on the fractional surface area as shown in EBSD 1000x micrographs [20]. These measurements showed that agglomerated BaTiO_3 content of the specimens were 8.1%, 8.0 and 3.6%, respectively, for the 0, 15 and 30 vol. % E-glass PMCs. We assume that the balance of the nanometer sized powder has been homogenized throughout the matrix, as shown by a micrograph at high magnification, 25000X, in Fig. 6. The content of dispersed BaTiO_3 is shown in Table 1. In addition to characterizing the distribution of constituents, the micrographs showed no evidence of voids that would result in a decrease in the PMC's measured dielectric constant.

The intent in this work was to manufacture a composite of two phases: (1) “matrix” of 10% BaTiO₃ nanoparticles dispersed in BECy resin and (2) micron sized glass reinforcement. However due to the agglomeration of the nanoparticles the resulting composite is a three phase system consisting of: (1) a “matrix” of BaTiO₃ nanoparticles dispersed in BECy resin; (2) micron sized BaTiO₃ agglomerates; and (3) micron sized glass reinforcement.

4.2 Effective Dielectric Constant

We compared the dielectric constant of a BaTiO₃/BECy PMC, calculated with the analytical model to the value empirically obtained at 1Hz, and found good correlation, Fig. 1. The BECy specimen loaded with 10 vol. % BaTiO₃ powder measured ϵ' ca. 5.8.

Fig. 4 shows the effective dielectric constant of the E-glass/BECy PMCs with and without BaTiO₃. As expected, E-glass/BECy composites without BaTiO₃ exhibit ϵ' values which rise with increasing glass fraction. The rise is explained by the disparity in ϵ' values of the E-glass, ca. 5.8, and the matrix, ca. 4, thus adding more glass naturally increases the composites' dielectric constant. The curves also show that the ϵ' values of the PMCs containing only unmodified BECy and E-glass fall below the values of E-glass PMCs prepared with the modified resin containing BaTiO₃. Furthermore, the curve of the PMC containing ~10 vol. % BaTiO₃ in BECy indicates a value in the range of 5.5 to 6.2, consistent with the targeted value of $\epsilon'=5.8$, matching the ϵ' value for the E-glass.

Contrary to our expectations, we observe an increase in ϵ' with increasing glass fraction for the E-glass/BaTiO₃/BECy composites. Recall that for these specimens, the dielectric constant value of the BaTiO₃/BECy “matrix” was tailored to match that of the glass. As such, we expected the PMC's ϵ' value to be independent of glass volume fraction. The reason for this trend is unclear. One possible explanation is the presence of the intensified electric fields induced at the interface of the matrix and E-glass microspheres that expose the much smaller BaTiO₃ nanometer sized particles to

augmented electric fields[21]. A similar argument can be made for the interface of the matrix and agglomerated BaTiO₃. These higher valued electric fields enhance the polarization of the dispersed ferroelectric nano-particles, Fig. 6, and produce a PMC ϵ' greater than that expected in the absence of the E-glass. The former would justify the correlation between increased PMC ϵ' values observed with increasing E-glass volume loading.

4.3 Breakdown Voltage and Dielectric Strength

Dielectric strength measurement of PMC's without BaTiO₃ were compared to those compounded with the ferroelectric nanometer sized powder. Fig. 7 shows that at 0 vol. % and 15 vol. % glass, the breakdown strength is significantly higher for the PMCs when the BECY matrix is modified with BaTiO₃. For the 30 vol. % glass specimen, however, there is no noticeable difference between the two specimen types.

A number of factors can influence the dielectric strength of a ceramic filled PMC, including filler size, wettability, and the homogeneity of the dispersion [13]. Our initial hypothesis was that by tailoring the resin's dielectric constant and taking advantage of dielectric constant matching with the E-glass filler, we could suppress the mismatch between matrix and glass and increase the composite's dielectric strength. From Fig. 7 we see that only at the lower E-glass loading do we have marked improvement. Furthermore, the results suggest that it is the BaTiO₃ which increased the breakdown strength, but not explicitly as a result of the dielectric constant matching.

While the presence of BaTiO₃ increased the breakdown strength for two of the specimens: 0 vol. % and 15 vol. % glass, the presence of glass microspheres did not appear to affect breakdown strength for either specimen type over the range of glass fractions studied. In other work, the addition of micron sized inclusions decreased the breakdown strength [22]. Since no such decrease was observed here, we cannot determine whether dielectric constant matching is a viable route for increasing breakdown strength in PMC's. More importantly,

since much of the BaTiO₃ nanopowder agglomerated instead of dispersing into the BECy, the composite cannot be considered as a simple two phase composite consisting of a nanocomposite “matrix” with dielectric constant matched to the micron sized glass particles. Instead, as mentioned earlier, it is a 3-phase composite consisting of: (1) a “matrix” of BaTiO₃ nanoparticles dispersed in BECy resin; (2) micron sized BaTiO₃ agglomerates; and (3) micron sized glass reinforcement. Considering the large dielectric constant of BaTiO₃, there is likely a significant mismatch in dielectric constant among these phases resulting in electric field concentration.

Developing more precise processing methods that closely control the homogenization and geometry of the wafers will permit us to improve processing of glass fiber reinforced PMC's that can serve multifunctional capacitive energy storage needs as well as fabrication of structurally sound components. Future studies should include higher glass fractions more relevant to those expected in structural composites, as well as better matching of matrix and reinforcement dielectric constants through better BaTiO₃ dispersion. Furthermore, using electrodes with increased areas, comparable to the sputtered surface, could result in breakdown within the constant electric field region, suspected to be greater in magnitude to that measured in the present study.

5 Conclusions

Dielectric strength measurements of PMCs containing a 10 vol. % BaTiO₃/BECy matrix, embedded with 0, 15 and 30 vol. % E-glass microspheres show that, in the case of 0 and 15 vol. % E-glass loading, there is a marked improvement in dielectric strength, Fig. 7. As a result, we measured increased applied voltages to our PMC wafers prior to catastrophic failure. This increase could lead to the development of structural capacitors with increased energy density. However, more studies are necessary to determine if the reduction in the dielectric constant mismatch is responsible for this increase in the structural dielectric's breakdown strength or if the observed phenomena is the result of some other interaction of the fillers with the matrix.

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Fig. 1. Bruggeman model of effective dielectric constant for BaTiO₃, at 1 Hz, as a function of ceramic filler vol. % loading in BECy resin.

Fig. 2. Typical gold-palladium sputter coated PMC using a 21mm diameter mask.

Fig. 3. PTFE tower with brass electrodes used to measure breakdown voltage.

Fig. 4. Mean dielectric constant values of PMC containing 0, 15 & 30 vol. % E-glass in a 10 vol. % BaTiO₃-BECy matrix over the range of frequencies from 1 to 10⁶ Hz.

Fig. 5 a) Back scattered electron diffraction micrograph of 15 vol. % E-glass/10 vol. % BaTiO₃ in BECy matrix. The heavier BaTiO₃ particles appear brighter than the grey E-glass and dark polymer. b) ImageJ areal calculation of agglomerated BaTiO₃ content.

Fig. 6 Unagglomerated BaTiO₃ particles dispersed in BECy matrix. Back scatter electron diffraction of 15 vol. % glass/10 vol. % BaTiO₃. Image taken at 25,000x.

Fig. 7. Dielectric breakdown strength measurements of PMCs with and without modified BECy resin matrix with reference to E-glass content.

Table 1: Calculated volume fraction loadings of dispersed BaTiO₃ in E-glass PMCs.

Specimen	Dispersed BaTiO ₃ (%)
0% E-glass/10% BaTiO ₃	1.9
15% E-glass/10% BaTiO ₃	2.0
30% E-glass/10% BaTiO ₃	6.4